

C-IMMSIM simulation results

May 7, 2025

Abstract

This document includes the plots relative to the simulation and the outcome of the epitope/peptide prediction used.

Produced by the C-IMMSIM Online server available at
<http://c-immsim.iac.rm.cnr.it> (alias to <http://kraken.iac.rm.cnr.it/C-IMMSIM>)

CITATIONS: For publication of results, please cite the following:

Nicolas Rapin, Ole Lund, Massimo Bernaschi, Filippo Castiglione. Computational Immunology Meets Bioinformatics: The Use of Prediction Tools for Molecular Binding in the Simulation of the Immune System. PLoS ONE 5(4): e9862
doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0009862, 2010

A retrospective validation

In-silico evaluation of adenoviral COVID-19 vaccination protocols: Assessment of immunological memory up to 6 months after the third dose. P. Stolfi, F. Castiglione, E. Mastrostefano, I. Di Biase, S. Di Biase, G. Palmieri, A. Prisco. Frontiers in Immunology, 13 (2022) doi: 10.3389/fimmu.2022.998262
<https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fimmu.2022.998262>

An in vivo validation

Identification and validation of viral antigens sharing sequence and structural homology with tumor associated antigens (TAAs). C. Ragone, C. Manolio, B. Cavalluzzo, A. Petrizzo, A. Mauriello, M-L. Tornesello, F. M. Buonaguro, F. Castiglione, L. Vitagliano, M. Ruvo, M. Tagliamonte, L. Buonaguro. Journal for ImmunoTherapy of Cancer. 9:e002694 (2021)
<https://jitc.bmj.com/content/9/5/e002694>

Original C-IMMSIM model: www.iac.cnr.it/~filippo/c-immsim

GETTING HELP:

Scientific problems: Filippo Castiglione ([filippo dot castiglione at cnr dot it](mailto:filippo.castiglione@cnr.it))

Technical problems: Ilaria Gonnella ([ilaria dot gonnella at cnr dot it](mailto:ilaria.gonnella@cnr.it))

Figure 1: Cell counts shown. Legend: Act=active, Intern=internalized the Ag, Pres II = presenting on MHC II, Dup = in the mitotic cycle, Anergic = anergic, Resting = not active.

Figure 2: Legend: symbols as figure above.

Figure 3: The virus, the immunoglobulins and the immunocomplexes.

Figure 4: Concentration of cytokines and interleukins. Inset plot shows danger signal together with leukocyte growth factor IL-2.


```

15]      pos=1113 len=5      LSGGE
16]      pos=1211 len=4      GQGS
17]      pos=1222 len=5      QDGTR
18]      pos=1333 len=12     GRRQRRRRSGDG
19]      pos=1398 len=22     KSSGGKGGSYSQAASSDSAQGS

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DoPeptideList_I:

Given the antigen injected creates the list of peptides for all the
NumAgProts proteins and for all i.e., 4 MHCI molecules

Read class I peptide list from file? NO

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Allele: A0201
Pseudo sequence: KAAHVEQRKAQTRTV
Threshold: 9.523800
Max score: 27.437000

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Antigen sequence file: /opt/lampp/htdocs/C-IMMSIM/Jobs/input/27330_20250507-071806_5_RECagKtObEKs.FSA_1_001

```

MLWHAMPPELNTARLMAGAGPAPMLAAAAGWQTLAALDAQAVELTARLNSLGEAWTGGGSDKALAAATPMVVWLQTAST
QAKTRAMQATAQAAAYTQAMATTPSLPEIAANHITQAVLTATNFFGINTIPIALTEMDYFIRMWNQAALAMEVYQAEAV
NTLFEKLEPMASILDPGASQSTTNPFIQMPSPGSSSTPVGQLPPAATQTLGQLGEMSGMPMQLTQPLQQVTSLSFQVGGTG
GGNPADEEAAQMGLLGTSPLSNHPLAGGSGPSAGAGLLRAESLPGAGGSLTRTPLMSQLIEKPVAPSVMPAAAAAGSSATG
GAAPVAGAMGGAQSGGSTRPGLVAPAPLAQEREDEDDWDEEDDMARGLQGVMLRSFGARDHTATVIETISIAPHF
VVRVMVSPTLFQDAEAEPAAWLRFWFPDPNGSNTEFQRAYTISEADPAAGRFAVDVVLHDPAGPASSWARTVKPGATIAV
MSLMGSSRFVPEEQPAGYLLIGDSASIPGMNGIETVNDVPIEMYLEQHDDNDTLIPLAKHPRLRVRWVMRRDEKSLA
EAIENRDWSDWYAWATPEAAALCKVVRRLRDEFQFPKSEIHAQAYWNAGRAMGTHRATEPAATEPEVGAAPQPESAVPAP
ARGSWRAQAASRLLAPLKLPLVLSGVLAAALVTLAQLAPFVLLVELSRLVSGAGAHRLFTVGFVAVGLLGTGALLAAALT
LWLHVIDARFARALRRLRLSKLSRLPLGWFTSRGSGSIKKLVTDLALHYLVTHAVPDAVAAVVAPVGVLVYLFVVDWR
VALVLFQVPLVYLTITSSLTIQSGPRIVQAQRWAEKMNAGEAGSYLEGQPVIRVFGAASSSFRRRLDEYIGFLVAWQRPLA
GKKTLMDLATRPATFLWLI AATGTLVATHRMDPVNLLPFMFLGTTFGARLLGIAYGLGLRTGLLAARHLQVTLDETEL
AVREHPREPLDGEAPATVVDHVTGFRYRGPVPIQDVSLTLRPGVTALVGPSPGSGKSTLATLLARFHDVERGAIIRVGGQ
DIRSLAADELYTRVGFVFLQEAQLVHGTAENIALAVPDPAEQVQVAAREAQIHDRVLRPDGYDTVLGANSGLSGGERQ
RLTIARAILGDTPVILDEATAFADPESEYLVQALNRLTRDRTVLVI AHRLHTITRADQIVVLDHGRIVERGTHEELLA
AGGRYRCLWDTGQGSRVAVAAAQDGRMSYMIATPAALTAATDIDIGSAVSVANAAVAATTGVLAAGGDEVLAATAR
LFNANAEEYHALSAQVAAFQTLFVRTLTGGCGVFRRRRGRQCVTAAEHRAAGARRRQRRRRSGDGQWRLRQRHFQCGGQ
PEFRQHSEHRRIVGIVAGLAVLAVVVIGAVVATVMCRRKSSGGKGGSYSQAASSDSAQGSVDVSLTA

```

Epitopes of protein 0 -----

```

0]      pos= 63 score=0.034595 unnormalised=5.3082000000 ALAAATPMV
1]      pos= 132 score=0.009986 unnormalised=1.5322000000 ALTEMDYFI
2]      pos= 161 score=0.002119 unnormalised=0.3252000000 TLFEKLEPM
3]      pos= 367 score=0.026351 unnormalised=4.0432000000 WMARGLQGV
4]      pos= 394 score=0.002341 unnormalised=0.3592000000 SIAPHFVRV
5]      pos= 499 score=0.011368 unnormalised=1.7442000000 LLIGDSASI
6]      pos= 509 score=0.003755 unnormalised=0.5762000000 GMNGIETV
7]      pos= 657 score=0.001787 unnormalised=0.2742000000 KLPLVLSGV
8]      pos= 661 score=0.018817 unnormalised=2.8872000000 VLSGVLAAAL
9]      pos= 671 score=0.034543 unnormalised=5.3002000000 TLAQLAPFV
10]     pos= 674 score=0.013720 unnormalised=2.1052000000 QLAPFVLLV
11]     pos= 706 score=0.000158 unnormalised=0.0242000000 GLLGTGALL
12]     pos= 712 score=0.001142 unnormalised=0.1752000000 ALLAAALTL
13]     pos= 775 score=0.006232 unnormalised=0.9562000000 AVPDAAVAV
14]     pos= 779 score=0.015024 unnormalised=2.3052000000 AVAAVVAPV
15]     pos= 792 score=0.023014 unnormalised=3.5312000000 YLFVVDWRV

```

16]	pos= 863	score=0.006075	unnormalised=0.9322000000	RLDEYIGFL
17]	pos= 870	score=0.007216	unnormalised=1.1072000000	FLVAWQRPL
18]	pos= 929	score=0.011622	unnormalised=1.7832000000	RLLGIAYGL
19]	pos= 944	score=0.007496	unnormalised=1.1502000000	LLAARHLQV
20]	pos= 953	score=0.005626	unnormalised=0.8632000000	TLDETELAV
21]	pos=1021	score=0.004146	unnormalised=0.6362000000	TLLARFHDV
22]	pos=1098	score=0.009425	unnormalised=1.4462000000	RLPDGYDTV
23]	pos=1135	score=0.015871	unnormalised=2.4352000000	ILDEATAFA
24]	pos=1229	score=0.029727	unnormalised=4.5612000000	YMIATPAAL
25]	pos=1265	score=0.014561	unnormalised=2.2342000000	VLAAGGDEV
26]	pos= -1	score=0.683283	unnormalised=104.8410000000	non-binding event

=====
Allele: A0203
Pseudo sequence: KAAHVEQRKKAQTRV
Threshold: 10.639400
Max score: 26.625000

Antigen sequence file: /opt/lampp/htdocs/C-IMMSIM/Jobs/input/27330_20250507-071806_5_RECagKt0bEKs.FSA_1_001

MLWHAMPPELNTARLMAGAGPAPMLAAAAGWQTLAALDAQAVELTARLNSLGEAWTGGGSDKALAAATPMVVWLQTAST
QAKTRAMQATAQAAAYTQAMATTPSLPEIAANHITQAVLTATNFFGINTIPIALTEMDFIRMWNQAALAMEVYQAEAV
NTLFEKLEPMASILDPGASQSTNPIFGMPSPGSSTPVGQLPPAATQTLGQLGEMSGPMQQLTQPLQQVTSLSFSQVGGTG
GGNPADEEAAQMGLLGTSPLSNHPLAGGSGPSAGAGLLRAESLPGAGGSLTRTPMSQLIEKPVAPSVMPAAAAGSSATG
GAAPVGAGAMGGAQSGGSTRPGLVAPAPLAQEREEDDEDDWDEEDDMARGLQGVMLRSFGARDHTATVIETISIAPHF
VRVRMVSPTLFQDAEAEPAAWLRFWFPDPNGSNTEFQRAYTISEADPAAGRFAVDVVLHDPAGPASSWARTVKPGATIAV
MSLMGSSRFVPEEQPAGYLLIGDSASIPGMNGI IETVPNDVPIEMYLEQHDDNDTLIPLAKHPRLRVRVWVRDEKSLA
EAIENRDWDWYAWATPEAAALCKCVRVRLRDEFGFPKSEIHAQAYWNAGRAMGTHRATEPAATEPEVGAAPQPESAVPAP
ARGSWRAQAASRLLAPLKLPLVLSGLVLAALVTLAQLAPFVLLVELSRLLVSGAGAHRLFTVGFAAVGLLGTGALLAAALT
LWLHVIDARFARALRRLLSKLSRLPLGWFTSRGSGSIKKLVTDLTLALHYLVTHAVPDAVAAVVAPVGLVYLVFVVDWR
VALVLFPGVLYLITITSSLTIQSGPRIVQAQRWAEKMNGEAGSYLEGQPVIRVFGAASSFRRLDEYIGFLVAWQRPLA
GKKTLMDLATRPATFLWLI AATGTLVATHRMPVNL LPMFLGTTFGARLLGIAYGLGLRTGLLAARHLQVTLDETEL
AVREHPREPLDGEAPATVVDHVTFGYRPGVPVIQDVSLTLRPGVTALVGPSPGSKSTLATLLARFHDVERGAI R VGGQ
DIRSLAADELYTRVGFVLQEAQLVHGTAENIALAVPDAPAEQVQVAAREAQIHDRVLR.LPDGYDTV.LGANSGLSGGERQ
RLTIARAILGDTPVILDEATAFADPESEYL VQALNRLTRDRTVLVI AHRLHTITRADQIVVLDHGRIVERGTHEELLA
AGGRYCRLLWDTGGSSRVAVAAAQDGTMSYMIATPAALTAATDIDIGISAVSVANA AAVAAATTGVLAAGGDEVLA A IAR
LFNANAEEYHALSAQVAFAFQTLFVRTLTGGCGVFRRRRGRQCVTAAEHRAAGARRRRRRSGDGQWRLRQQRHFQCGGGQ
PEFRQHSEHRRIVIGAVGLAVLVVIGAVVATVMCRKSSGGKGGSYSQAASSDSAQGSVSLTA

Epitopes of protein 0 -----
0] pos= 4 score=0.004837 unnormalised=0.6506000000 AMPPELNTA
1] pos= 63 score=0.030389 unnormalised=4.0876000000 ALAAATPMV
2] pos= 367 score=0.039601 unnormalised=5.3266000000 WMARGLQGV
3] pos= 394 score=0.007446 unnormalised=1.0016000000 SIAPHFVRV
4] pos= 499 score=0.016762 unnormalised=2.2546000000 LLIIGDSASI
5] pos= 657 score=0.006272 unnormalised=0.8436000000 KLPLVLSGV
6] pos= 661 score=0.004190 unnormalised=0.5636000000 VLSGVLAAL
7] pos= 671 score=0.024315 unnormalised=3.2706000000 TLAQLAPFV
8] pos= 674 score=0.015476 unnormalised=2.0816000000 QLAPFVLLV
9] pos= 775 score=0.016346 unnormalised=2.1986000000 AVPDAVAAV
10] pos= 779 score=0.021461 unnormalised=2.8866000000 AVAAVVAPV
11] pos= 944 score=0.004748 unnormalised=0.6386000000 LLAARHLQV
12] pos=1098 score=0.007342 unnormalised=0.9876000000 RLPDGYDTV
13] pos=1229 score=0.021371 unnormalised=2.8746000000 YMIATPAAL
14] pos= -1 score=0.779444 unnormalised=104.8410000000 non-binding event

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Allele: B0702
Pseudo sequence: KAAREEQIKAQTRE
Threshold: 8.702800

Max score: 28.406000

Antigen sequence file: /opt/lampp/htdocs/C-IMMSIM/Jobs/input/27330_20250507-071806_5_RECagKtObEKs.FSA_1_001

MLWHAMPPELNTARLMAGAPMLAAAAGWQTLAALDAQAVELTARLNSLGEAWTGGGSDKALAAATPMVVVLQTAST
QAKTRAMQATAQAAAYTQAMATTPSLPEIAANHITQAVLTATNFFGINTIPIALTEMDFYIRMWNQAALAMEVYQAEAV
NTLFEKLEPMASILDPGASQSTTNPIFGMPSPGSSTPVGQLPPAATQTLGQLGEMSGPMQQLTQPLQQVTSLSFSQVGGTG
GGNPADEEAAQMGLLGTSPLSNHPLAGGSGPSAGAGLLRAESLPGAGGSLTRTPLMSQLIEKPVAPSVMPAAAAGSSATG
GAAPVAGAGAMGQAQSGGSTRPLVAPLAQEREEDDEDDWDEEDDMARGLQGVMLRSFGARDHTATVIETISIAPIHF
VRVMVSPTLFQDAEAEPAAWLRFWFPDPNGSNTEFQRAYTISEADPAAGRFADVVLHDPAGPASSWARTVKPGATIAV
MSLMGSSRFDVPEEQPAGYLLIGDSASIPGMNGIETVPNDVPIEMYLEQHDDNDTLIPLAKHPRLRVRWVMMRDEKSLA
EAIENRDWSWYAWATPEAAAALCVRVRLRDEFQPKSEIHAQAYWNAGRAMGTHRATEPAATEPEVGAAPQPESAVPAP
ARGSWRAQAASRLAPLKLPLVLSGVLAALVTLAQLAPFVLLVELSRLLVSGAGAHRLFTVGFVAVGLLGTGALLAAALT
LWLHVIDARFARALRLRLSKLSRLPLGWTSRSGSISIKLVTDLALHYLVTHAVPDAVAVAVPVGLVYLVFVVDWR
VALVLFPGVLYLTTITSSLTIQSGPRIVQAQRWAEKMNGEAGSYLEGQPVIRVFGAASSFRRLDEYIGFLVAWQRPLA
GKKTLMDLATRPAFLWLIAATGTLVATHRMDPVNLLPFMFLGTFGARLLGIAYGLGGLRTGLLAARHLQVTLDETEL
AVREHPREPLDGEAPATVVDHVTFGYRPGVPVIQDVSLTLRPGTVTALVGPSSGKSTLALLARFHDVERGAIRVGGQ
DIRSLAADELYTRVGFVQEAQLVHGTAENIALAVPDPAEQVQVAAREAQIHDRVLRPLDGYDVLGANSGLSGGERQ
RLTIARAILGDTPVILDEATAFADPESEYLVQALNRLTRDRTVLVIARHLHTITRADQIVVLHDHGRIVERGTHEELLA
AGGRYRCLWDTGGQSRVAVAAAQDGRMSYMIATPAALTAATDIDGIGSAVSVANAAVAATTVGLAAGGDEVLAATAR
LFNANAEEYHALSAQVAAFQTLFVRTLTGCGCFVRRRRGRQCVTAAEHRRAAGARRRRRRSGDQWRLRQRHFHFCGGQ
PEFRQHSEHRRIVGIVAGLAVLAVVVIGAVVATVMCRKSSGGKGSYSQAASSDSAQGSVSLTA

Epitopes of protein 0 -----

0]	pos= 19	score=0.016443	unnormalised=3.080200000	GPAPMLAAA
1]	pos= 21	score=0.004314	unnormalised=0.808200000	APMLAAAAG
2]	pos= 102	score=0.007811	unnormalised=1.463200000	TPSLPEIAA
3]	pos= 188	score=0.013416	unnormalised=2.513200000	MPSPGSSTP
4]	pos= 195	score=0.009311	unnormalised=1.744200000	TPVGQLPPA
5]	pos= 200	score=0.035672	unnormalised=6.682200000	LPPAATQTL
6]	pos= 223	score=0.011719	unnormalised=2.195200000	QPLQQVTSL
7]	pos= 269	score=0.018264	unnormalised=3.421200000	GPSAGAGLL
8]	pos= 304	score=0.020954	unnormalised=3.925200000	APSVMPAAA
9]	pos= 308	score=0.021120	unnormalised=3.956200000	MPAAAAGSS
10]	pos= 368	score=0.006274	unnormalised=1.175200000	MARGLQGVM
11]	pos= 396	score=0.017404	unnormalised=3.260200000	APHFVRVRM
12]	pos= 401	score=0.005142	unnormalised=0.963200000	RVRMVSPTL
13]	pos= 445	score=0.007154	unnormalised=1.340200000	DPAAGRFVAV
14]	pos= 472	score=0.006834	unnormalised=1.280200000	KPGATIAVM
15]	pos= 537	score=0.009968	unnormalised=1.867200000	IPLAKHPRL
16]	pos= 542	score=0.028086	unnormalised=5.261200000	HPRLRVRWV
17]	pos= 636	score=0.028406	unnormalised=5.321200000	VPAPARGSW
18]	pos= 638	score=0.007379	unnormalised=1.382200000	APARGSWRA
19]	pos= 654	score=0.018536	unnormalised=3.472200000	APLKLPLVL
20]	pos= 658	score=0.017217	unnormalised=3.225200000	LPLVLSGVV
21]	pos= 676	score=0.007811	unnormalised=1.463200000	APFVLLVEL
22]	pos= 729	score=0.004266	unnormalised=0.799200000	FARALRLRL
23]	pos= 785	score=0.002729	unnormalised=0.511200000	APVGLVYVL
24]	pos= 876	score=0.030035	unnormalised=5.626200000	RPLAGKCTL
25]	pos= 890	score=0.007064	unnormalised=1.323200000	RPATFLWLI
26]	pos= 946	score=0.010704	unnormalised=2.005200000	AARHLQVTL
27]	pos= 990	score=0.004779	unnormalised=0.895200000	VPVIQDVSL
28]	pos=1001	score=0.009226	unnormalised=1.728200000	RPGTVTALV
29]	pos=1010	score=0.003701	unnormalised=0.693200000	GPSGSGKST
30]	pos=1078	score=0.012685	unnormalised=2.376200000	APAEQVQVA
31]	pos=1233	score=0.035901	unnormalised=6.725200000	TPAALTAAT
32]	pos= -1	score=0.559676	unnormalised=104.841000000	non-binding event

Allele: B5301
Pseudo sequence: KAAREEQIKTQTRE

Threshold: 8.175800
Max score: 25.226000

Antigen sequence file: /opt/lampp/htdocs/C-IMMSIM/Jobs/input/27330_20250507-071806_5_RECagKtObEKs.FSA_1_001

MLWHAMPPELNTARLMAGAGPAPMLAAAAGWQTLAALDAQVELTARLNSLGEAWTGGGSDKALAAATPMVVWLQTAST
QAKTRAMQATAQAAAAYTQAMATTPSLPEIAANHITQAVLTATNFFGINTIPIALTEMDYFIRMWNQAALAMEVYQAETAV
NTLFEKLEPMASILDPGASQSTTNPFGMPSPGSSTPVGQLPPAATQTLGQLGEMSGPMQQLTQPLQQVTSLSFSQVGGTG
GGNPADEEAAQMGLLGTSPLSNHLPLAGGSGPSAGAGLLRAESLPGAGGSLTRTPMLMSQLIEKPVAPSVMPAAAAAGSSATG
GAAPVAGAGMGQAQSGGSTRPLVAPAPLAQEREDEDDWDEEDDWMARGLQGVMLRSFGARDHTATVIETISIAPHF
VRVRMVSPTLFDAAEPAAWLRFWFPDPNGSNTEFQRAYTISEADPAAGRFAVDVVLHDPAGPASSWARTVKPGATIAV
MSLMGSSRFVPEEQPAGYLLIGDSASIPGMNGIETVPNDVPIEMYLEQHDDNDTLIPLAKHPRLRVRWVRRDEKSLA
EAIENRDWDWYAWATPEAAALKCVRVRLRDEFQFPKSEIHAQAYWNAGRAMGTHRATEPAATEPEVGAAPQPESAVPAP
ARGSWRAQAASRL LAPLKLPLVLSGVLAAALVTLAQLAPFVLLVELSRLLVSGAGAHRLFTVGFVAAVLLGTGALLAAALT
LWLHVIDARFARALRRLRLSKLSRLPLGWFTSRGSGSIKKLVTDDTLALHYLVTHAVPDAVAVVAPVGVLYLVFVVDWR
VALVLFPGVLYLTISSSLTIQSGPRIVQQRWAEKMNGEAGSYLEGQPVIRVFGAASSSFRRRLDEYIGFLVAWQRPLA
GKKTMLDLATRPATFLWLIAATGTLVATHRMDPVNLLPFMFLGTTFGARLLGIA YGLGLRTGLLAARHLQVTLDETEL
AVREHPREPLDGEAPATVVFDPHVTGFRPVPVVIQDVSLTRPGVTALVGPSSGKSTLTLARFHDVERGAIIRVGGQ
DIRSLAADELYTRVGFVQLQEAQLVHGTAENIALAVDPAPAEQVQVAAREAQIHDRVLRVLPDGYDVLGANSGLSGGERQ
RLTIARA ILGDTPVILDEATAFADPESEYLQQLNRLTRDRTVLVI AHRHLHTITRADQIVVLDHGRIVERGTHEELLA
AGGRYCRWLWDTGGGSRVAVAAAQDGTTRMSYMIATPAALTAATDIDIGISAVSVANA AAVAAATTGVLAAGGDEVLAATAR
LFNANAEEYHALSAQVAFAFQTLFVRTLTGGCGVFRRRRGRQCVTAAEHRAAGARRRRRRSGDGQWRLRQQRHFHFCGGGQ
PEFRQHSEHRRIVGIVAGLAVLAVVVIGAVVATVMCRRKSSGGKGGSYSAASSDSAQGSVSLTA

Epitopes of protein 0 -----

0]	pos=	15	score=0.004592	unnormalised=0.7432000000	MAGAGPAPM
1]	pos=	87	score=0.018934	unnormalised=3.0642000000	QATAQAAAY
2]	pos=	91	score=0.004747	unnormalised=0.7682000000	QAAAAYTQAM
3]	pos=	97	score=0.002090	unnormalised=0.3382000000	QAMATTPSL
4]	pos=	105	score=0.008516	unnormalised=1.3782000000	LPEIAANHI
5]	pos=	115	score=0.005575	unnormalised=0.9022000000	QAVLTATNF
6]	pos=	200	score=0.014189	unnormalised=2.2962000000	LPPAATQTL
7]	pos=	223	score=0.004716	unnormalised=0.7632000000	QPLQQVTSL
8]	pos=	391	score=0.016215	unnormalised=2.6242000000	ETISIAPHF
9]	pos=	412	score=0.009363	unnormalised=1.5152000000	DAEAEPAAW
10]	pos=	416	score=0.034920	unnormalised=5.6512000000	EPAAWLRFW
11]	pos=	427	score=0.036143	unnormalised=5.8492000000	DPNGSNTEF
12]	pos=	443	score=0.008411	unnormalised=1.3612000000	EADPAAGRF
13]	pos=	445	score=0.004697	unnormalised=0.7602000000	DPAAGRFVAV
14]	pos=	459	score=0.054508	unnormalised=8.8212000000	DPAGPASSW
15]	pos=	480	score=0.006489	unnormalised=1.0502000000	MSLMGSSRF
16]	pos=	490	score=0.012835	unnormalised=2.0772000000	VPEEQPAGY
17]	pos=	517	score=0.012977	unnormalised=2.1002000000	VPNDVPIEM
18]	pos=	573	score=0.005216	unnormalised=0.8442000000	WATPEAAAL
19]	pos=	618	score=0.011420	unnormalised=1.8482000000	EPAATEPEV
20]	pos=	636	score=0.028623	unnormalised=4.6322000000	VPAPARGSW
21]	pos=	658	score=0.003221	unnormalised=0.5212000000	LPLVLSGVL
22]	pos=	890	score=0.007979	unnormalised=1.2912000000	RPATFLWLI
23]	pos=	912	score=0.018916	unnormalised=3.0612000000	DPVNLLPFM
24]	pos=	990	score=0.007144	unnormalised=1.1562000000	VPVIQDVSL
25]	pos=	1099	score=0.009733	unnormalised=1.5752000000	LPDGYDVL
26]	pos=	-1	score=0.647830	unnormalised=104.8410000000	non-binding event

DoPeptideList_II:

Given the antigen injected creates the list of peptides for all the
NumAgProts proteins and for all i.e., 2 MHCII molecules

Read class II peptide list from file? NO

=====
Allele: DRB3_0101
Pseudo sequence: RVTLGRDAYW
Threshold: 2.631130
Max score: 27.850000

Antigen sequence file: /opt/lampp/htdocs/C-IMMSIM/Jobs/input/27330_20250507-071806_5_RECagKtObEKs.FSA_1_001

```
MLWHAMPPELNTARLMAGAGPAPMLAAAAGWQTLAALDAQVELTARLNSLGEAWTGGGSDKALAAATPMVVWLQTAST
QAKTRAMQATAQAAAYTQAMATTPSLPEIAANHITQAVLTATNFFGINTIPIALTEMDFYIRMWNQAALAMEVYQAETAV
NTLFEKLEPMASILDPGASQSTTNPFGMPSPGSSPTVGGQLPPAATQTLGQLGEMSGPMQQLTQLPQQVTSLSFSQVGGTG
GGNPADEEAAQMGLLGTSPLSNHPLAGGSGPSAGAGLLRAESLPGAGGSLTRTPLMSQLIEKPVAPSVMPAAAAAGSSATG
GAAPVGAGAMGQGAQSGGSTRPGLVAPAPLAQEREDEDDWDEEDDMARGLQGVMLRSFGARDHTATVIETISIAPHF
VRVRMVSPTLFDQAAEAEPAAWLRFWFPDPNGSNTEFQRAYTISEADPAAGRFAVDVVLDHPAGPASSWARTVKPGATIAV
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23]	pos=	810	score=0.001231	unnormalised=0.3048700000	VYLTITSSL
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Allele: DRB1_0101
Pseudo sequence: KFAHVEQRKAQTRV
Threshold: 2.392440
Max score: 26.461000

Antigen sequence file: /opt/lampp/htdocs/C-IMMSIM/Jobs/input/27330_20250507-071806_5_RECagKtObEKs.FSA_1_001

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Epitopes of protein 0 -----

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